

“The DeNATOisation” of Ukraine and Eastern Europe as a Principal Objective of Russia’s War against Ukraine

Tetiana Sydoruk¹, Bohdan Hryhorash ² and Mariia Avhustiuk ³

Abstract

The paper explores the core concept of “deNATOisation” as articulated by the Kremlin and its contemporary implications within the context of the Russian Federation’s full-scale war against Ukraine. Significant attention is devoted to analyzing the historical background of this policy, viewed through the lens of the evolution of relations between Russia and NATO in the post-bipolar era. Concurrently, the current reasons for Russian opposition to NATO expansion are examined, particularly those related to security, ideology, and domestic politics. Employing qualitative methods to analyze a range of documentary and secondary sources, the authors present arguments that demonstrate the Russian government’s misinterpretation of history, highlighting how the distortion of historical facts provides a fertile ground for manipulation and potentially perilous scenarios in the resolution of the Russian-Ukrainian conflict.

Keywords

NATO; Ukraine; Russian Federation; deNATOisation; Russian-Ukrainian war

¹ Tetiana Sydoruk (ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7468-7672>) is a Professor of Political Science and Head of the Department of International Relations at the National University of Ostroh Academy in Ukraine. She works on EU enlargement policy, the Eastern Partnership, European security, and the Russian-Ukrainian war. E-mail: tetiana.sydoruk@oa.edu.ua.

² Bohdan Hryhorash (ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0007-2636-8822>) has a master’s degree in International Relations, Public Communications, and Regional Studies from the National University of Ostroh Academy in Ukraine. His research interests include EU foreign policy, Euro-Atlantic security architecture, European security, and the Russian-Ukrainian war. E-mail: bohdan.hryhorash@oa.edu.ua.

³ Mariia Avhustiuk (ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9510-5715>) is a Professor of International Relations at the National University of Ostroh Academy in Ukraine. Her research interests include EU, NATO, European security, and the Russian-Ukrainian war. E-mail: mariia.avgustiuk@oa.edu.ua.

Introduction

Nearly three and a half years have passed since the Kremlin initiated its so-called “special military operation” against Ukraine, purportedly aimed at its “demilitarization” and “denazification” – namely, the disarmament and removal of the democratically elected government in Kyiv. These efforts continue despite the enormous human and financial costs incurred by Russia. However, this represents only part of the narrative. In fact, Moscow’s strategic objectives extend far beyond Ukraine, encompassing aims such as the deNATOisation of its wider neighborhood.

The idea of deNATOisation, essentially reducing NATO’s presence and influence in Eastern Europe and the post-Soviet space, has been a recurring theme in the official rhetoric of Russian leaders for decades. This narrative emerged after the Cold War, following the collapse of the Soviet Union and the creation of the Russian Federation. It gained renewed momentum after key events such as Ukraine’s Orange Revolution, the Revolution of Dignity, Russia’s hybrid war in 2014, and the full-scale invasion of Ukraine. These turning points breathed new life into the Kremlin’s long-standing concerns about NATO’s expansion. One of Moscow’s key goals in the current war is to push back against NATO’s presence in what it sees as its traditional sphere of influence and to prevent the Alliance from gaining ground in the post-Soviet region. The issue of Ukraine potentially joining NATO remains especially sensitive and troubling for the Kremlin.

To date, a considerable body of scholarly work has been dedicated to the issue of NATO’s eastward expansion and the corresponding response of the Russian Federation. These studies have variously examined the strategic prudence or imprudence of such enlargement, the perceived “betrayal” of the Russian Federation by the Alliance, the alleged breach of “assurance policies” reportedly provided to Gorbachev and Yeltsin regarding NATO’s non-expansion, and the extent to which the Alliance bears “responsibility” for the outbreak of the Russian-Ukrainian war – or, conversely, arguments justifying the absence of such culpability.

By contrast, significantly less scholarly attention has been directed towards the contemporary objectives pursued by the Russian Federation in its confrontation with Ukraine and NATO, as well as the underlying motives of this confrontation. Within Ukrainian academic discourse, the theme of deNATOisation has been often addressed (Ohryzko, Sohn & Gic, 2024; Sydoruk & Pavliuk, 2022; Sydoruk, Pavliuk & Shuliak, 2023). In Western scholarship, the implications of NATO enlargement vis-à-vis Russia’s security interests have also been explored (Ciuriak, 2023; Haslam, 2024; Maitra, 2021; Milano, 1998; Sarotte, 2025; Schuette, 2023). Overall, the historical origins of the notion of deNATOisation remain contested within academic debate, as do the fundamental causes of Russia’s war against Ukraine. Misinterpretations of historical developments rooted in erroneous assumptions regarding the causes and motivations behind the war risk producing a short-sighted resolution to the conflict. Such a settlement could enable the resumption of Russian aggression in Europe whenever it suits the strategic aims of the Kremlin.

Recent research, declassified documents, and the shift in Washington’s policy towards attempting to remove the issue of Ukraine’s NATO membership from the agenda have all sparked further debate regarding NATO’s enlargement as a possible cause of the Russo-Ukrainian war. Overall, two dominant narratives characterized this discourse even prior to Russia’s full-scale invasion of Ukraine. The first, predominantly associated with proponents of neorealism, viewed attempts to integrate Kyiv into NATO as perilous and advocated seeking compromises with Russia, which were deemed preferable to the prospect of war (Charap, 2022; Kimmage, 2022; Maitra, 2021). Several scholars, continuing the tradition initiated by John J. Mearsheimer (2014), argue that NATO’s eastward

expansion constituted an unnecessary provocation that incentivized Putin's aggressive actions towards neighboring states. For instance, Charles Kupchan contends that expanding NATO and constructing a European security order after the Cold War that consolidated Western power against Russia was a fundamental error (Foreign Affairs, 2022).

The second narrative, typical of proponents of liberal internationalism, viewed Russia as an imperialist state seeking to dominate its neighbors, criticized the West for its failure to contain Russia in previous years, and called for active resistance against Putin (see, for example, Edelman & Kramer, 2022; McFaul, 2022).

Overall, the neorealist thesis that NATO enlargement provoked revanchism in Russia remains unproven. Nevertheless, this argument forms the basis for contemporary authors who claim that Russia's "legitimate objections" to Ukraine's NATO membership fully or partly motivated its 2022 invasion of Ukraine. This approach views Kremlin actions merely as a reaction to waves of NATO expansion and US policy. But what of Moscow's own strategic objectives and its proactive, rather than reactive, measures towards NATO? This is an exceptionally important political question, yet it has been scarcely examined. In this article, we offer an analysis of Russia's aims through the lens of the concept of deNATOisation of Ukraine and the wider Eastern Europe, a notion increasingly prominent in the Kremlin's foreign policy narratives.

The objective of this paper is to examine the conceptual nature of deNATOisation and its contemporary significance within the context of the full-scale war initiated by the Russian Federation against Ukraine. Particular emphasis is placed on the historical foundations of this policy, explored through the lens of Russia-NATO relations in the post-bipolar international order. Simultaneously, the study considers current motivations underpinning Russia's resistance to the enlargement of the Alliance, including security concerns, ideological imperatives, and domestic political factors.

The present study employs qualitative research methods to examine both primary sources – including treaties, contracts, strategic doctrines, official declarations, and political speeches – and secondary sources such as scholarly publications, analytical reports, and media materials relevant to the topic under consideration. To elucidate the nature and development of the Russian concept of deNATOisation a broad range of documents was scrutinized. Additionally, the authors conducted an in-depth review of academic literature and monographs that contribute to the ongoing and contentious debate regarding whether NATO's eastward enlargement constitutes the fundamental cause of tensions in NATO-Russia relations and, by extension, the Kremlin's aggressive military campaign against Ukraine. This analysis enabled the authors to formulate a series of arguments demonstrating the Russian government's misrepresentation of historical events. Furthermore, the study highlights how the distortion of historical narratives fosters an environment conducive to manipulation and poses significant risks in the context of conflict resolution.

The current President of the United States, Donald Trump, appears to subscribe to the belief that the policies of his predecessor, Joseph Biden, along with the actions of the Ukrainian leadership, "compelled" the Russian Federation to initiate its full-scale invasion. According to this narrative, President Biden's alleged assurances regarding prospective NATO membership for Ukraine provoked Russia's military response, while the Ukrainian authorities are criticized for their unwillingness to accommodate the Kremlin's demands. However, a critical examination of available sources indicates that the Russian Federation's intent to "deNATOize" neighboring states does not stem from any actual betrayal by Western actors or from legitimate concerns regarding threats posed by the North Atlantic Alliance to Russian national security. Rather, it is strategically advantageous for the Kremlin to promote such a narrative, thereby deflecting accountability for the unlawful aggression against a sovereign state,

the primary aim of which appears to be the obstruction of Ukraine's pursuit of an independent civilizational trajectory. Should any prospective peace agreement or settlement concerning the Russian-Ukrainian conflict be predicated upon a misrepresentation of the war's origins and causes, such an arrangement is likely to prove unsustainable and may ultimately be consigned to the annals of failed historical precedents. Regarded as a "legitimate concern" of Russia, and thus closing the door to Ukraine's NATO membership, this is not an act of strategic prudence likely to encourage Putin to end the war, but rather a short-sighted approach based on the illusion of "giving the arsonist two rooms in order to extinguish the fire in the house".

The concept of deNATOisation

Before proceeding with an analysis of the Russian Federation's objectives regarding opposition to the development and further expansion of NATO, it is pertinent to first define the concept of deNATOisation. Broadly, the Russian understanding of deNATOisation encapsulates the Kremlin's objective to curtail NATO's influence and presence in post-socialist states that are members of the alliance, to eliminate such influence in post-Soviet nations with close ties to the Alliance, and to prevent their future accession. This notion constitutes a key element of Russian foreign policy, particularly under the presidency of Volodymyr Putin. It emerged as a response to NATO's eastward expansion following the end of the Cold War. The core of this policy was most clearly articulated in the "Putin ultimatum" presented to the United States and NATO on December 17, 2021, which called for: "...the refusal of any NATO expansion [eastwards], the cessation of military cooperation with post-Soviet countries, the withdrawal of American nuclear weapons from Europe, and the removal of NATO forces to the 1997 borders" (Thom, 2021). In effect, this demand implied the withdrawal of NATO's military bases from the 14 European nations that had joined the alliance between 1999 and 2020.

To gain a deeper understanding of the general and specific objectives of the Russian Federation, it is pertinent to examine in greater detail the provisions outlined in the "ultimatum" of 17 December 2021. This analysis will enable the identification of the key components of the concept of deNATOisation. Since the autumn of 2021, Russia has stationed over 150,000 military personnel along its borders with Ukraine, simultaneously issuing threats of "military-technical measures" should NATO persist in its cooperation with Ukraine and should Russia fail to secure security assurances from the West. In December of the same year, the Kremlin unilaterally drafted two highly aggressive documents, which it regarded as essential to averting military conflict in Ukraine. These proposals, articulated in a draft agreement with NATO and a draft treaty with the United States, were formally published by the Russian Ministry of Foreign Affairs and subsequently delivered to the relevant parties.

A Preliminary Draft of the Russia-NATO Agreement. The objectives of deNATOisation were pursued through a range of specific provisions, outlined as follows (MID RF 2021b): A prohibition on the deployment of foreign armed forces and weapons within the territories of European states that were not members of NATO as of 1997 (article 4); A restriction on the establishment of medium- and short-range missile deployment zones (article 5); A ban on the expansion of NATO, with particular emphasis on the prohibition of Ukraine's accession to the Alliance (article 6); and a complete prohibition of NATO military activities within the territory of Ukraine, as well as in other states in Eastern Europe, the South Caucasus, and Central Asia (article 7).

A Preliminary Draft of the Russia-USA Treaty. This document, in turn, elaborates upon and specifies the requirements set forth by the Russian Federation (MID RF 2021a): the prohibition of the establishment of military bases by the United States within the territories of the former Soviet Union, alongside the cessation of any further development of bilateral military cooperation with the United

States (article 4); the imposition of restrictions on the deployment of armed forces beyond the national territories of the Russian Federation (article 5); the prohibition of the deployment of medium- and short-range missiles outside the national borders of the Russian Federation (article 6); the prohibition of the deployment of nuclear weapons outside national territories, along with the repatriation of any nuclear weapons previously deployed abroad. This includes the dismantling of infrastructure intended for the deployment of nuclear weapons outside the Russian Federation (article 7). Additionally, the training of military personnel and civilians from non-nuclear-armed states in the use of such weapons is prohibited. The conduct of exercises or training sessions that simulate scenarios involving the use of nuclear weapons is also forbidden.

The aggressive and unacceptable terms outlined in these drafts, along with the atmosphere in which they were presented (at a time when the Russian Federation was actively reinforcing its military presence along the Ukrainian border), serve to reflect Moscow's long-standing political objectives, as articulated over several years (Lanoszka, 2021). It is also significant to observe that the maximalist provisions within both draft agreements, their subsequent publication by the Russian government, and the imperious language framing the Russian Federation's demands, collectively indicated that the Kremlin had likely anticipated a rejection. By amassing substantial military forces on the Ukrainian border, Moscow leveraged the refusal to engage in discussions regarding these drafts as yet another pretext and justification for military action against Ukraine (Pifer, 2021).

These draft treaties provide a clear indication of the Kremlin's strategic intentions about Ukraine. In his ultimatum, Putin essentially declared that Ukraine's existence and territorial integrity were contingent upon its submission to Russia, a stance that has been repeatedly and unequivocally rejected by the Ukrainian people. This was not a call for Ukrainian neutrality, but rather a demand for Ukraine's integration into the Russian sphere of influence, as delineated in the so-called "Putin ultimatum." Consequently, in December 2021, Putin issued a demand to the United States and NATO, aimed at compelling the West to relinquish the principle of Ukrainian sovereignty, whilst further advancing NATO's partnership along its eastern flank and paving the way for its future expansion (Bugayova, Stepanenko & Kagan, 2023).

The outcome of sustained diplomatic engagement between American, European, and Russian diplomats in the latter part of 2021 and early 2022 culminated in a firm rejection of the Kremlin's demands by the Biden administration and its allies. Acceptance of these demands would have contravened the fundamental principles enshrined in several key international agreements: the Washington Treaty of 1949, which established the North Atlantic Treaty Organization (NATO); the Charter of the United Nations (1945); the Helsinki Final Act (1975); the Paris Charter for a New Europe (1990); and the Charter for European Security (1999). These documents uphold the right of every state to independently determine and alter its security arrangements. Moreover, agreeing to such demands would have left Ukraine in a precarious "grey zone" and implied NATO's recognition of President Volodymyr Putin's claims over a sphere of influence. On 24 February 2022, Russia commenced a full-scale invasion of Ukraine.

Throughout the conflict, the concept of deNATOisation of Ukraine was frequently articulated by representatives of the Russian government and its diplomatic corps. However, the term itself did not achieve the same level of prominence as the closely associated terms "denazification" and "demilitarization". The most explicit invocation of this concept occurred during the speech of the head of the Russian delegation, K. Gavrylov, at the 1074th plenary meeting of the OSCE Forum for Security and Cooperation on April 17, 2024. In his address, Gavrylov stated: "...to safeguard the interests of national security, the Russian Federation, in full compliance with Article 51 of the UN Charter, was

compelled to initiate a special military operation. Presently, the strategies of the United States and NATO envisage maintaining Ukraine – at least in part – as an anti-Russian enclave entirely under their control, designed to serve the interests of the bloc... Under these circumstances, the objectives of demilitarization and deNATOization of Ukraine remain pertinent to us..." (OBSE 2024).

Historical background of the concept of deNATOisation

Most scholars examining the issue of NATO enlargement appropriately regard it as a pivotal moment in the broader process of the Alliance's eastern expansion, which was catalyzed by the reunification of Germany in 1990. Following the fall of the Berlin Wall, the unification of the two German states became feasible only after the Soviet Union, the United States, France, and the United Kingdom reached a consensus on the matter. For the Western powers, the primary objective was to persuade the USSR. Archival documents, along with the memoirs of the Federal Republic of Germany's Minister of Foreign Affairs, Hans-Dietrich Genscher, reveal that he and US Secretary of State James Baker discussed Genscher's proposal "to reassure the Soviets that NATO would not extend its territorial reach to the territory of the GDR nor anywhere else in Eastern Europe..." (Sarotte 2025) during his visit to Washington on 2 February 1990.

However, by the end of that same month, Baker wrote to Genscher stating that "discussions of NATO's jurisdiction should be avoided in the future when describing our common position on Germany's NATO relationship" (Sarotte 2025). This shift in stance was likely a result of President George H.W. Bush's decision that the most effective means of securing Moscow's consent for German reunification was not through placing limitations on NATO's future but rather through offering Germany financial support, including loans and other forms of aid to the USSR, in exchange for the country's unity. Federal Chancellor Helmut Kohl concurred with Bush's decisive conclusion: "You've got deep pockets." (Sarotte 2025).

At the meeting in July 1990, the German leader obtained approval for the reunification of the country from the Soviet head of state, Mykhailo Gorbachov. On 12 September 1990, foreign ministers signed the "2+4 Agreement" in Moscow, which regulated the borders and the future status of Germany (Deutschland.de 2017). It is likely that, during the negotiations, Western officials provided some verbal assurances to the Soviet Union concerning the future of NATO, employing various formulations. Scholars in this field predominantly suggest that the Soviet Union may have been "led to believe" that NATO would not expand. However, such assurances were not formally enshrined in the treaty and were not documented in any official texts. Moreover, the "2+4 Agreement" concerned only Germany and allowed NATO forces stationed abroad to redeploy to the territory of the former German Democratic Republic at the discretion of the German government, after the withdrawal of all Soviet forces from the GDR. This provision did not prohibit the movement of NATO forces eastward. As for the future expansion of NATO and the inclusion of Warsaw Pact countries in the Alliance, the text of the "2+4 Agreement" made did not refer to this, as the Warsaw Pact remained in effect at that time (Pifer 2014). At that juncture, no one could have predicted the speed with which the so-called "socialist bloc" – that is, the Soviet occupation zone in Europe – would disappear, along with the Soviet Union itself.

History contains certain fixed points. Moscow signed and ratified a treaty in 1990 that permitted the extension of NATO's jurisdiction eastwards; beyond the Cold War front line. This represented a diplomatic failure for the Soviet Union: although certain Western participants broached the topic of a comprehensive prohibition on the expansion of the alliance during negotiations, such a provision is conspicuously absent from the text of the treaty.

Following the dissolution of the USSR, a new phase in Moscow-NATO relations emerged. During the early 1990s, the Kremlin signaled an interest in deepening its ties with the West, particularly with NATO. President B. Yeltsin even suggested that the Russian Federation might eventually join NATO (Sydoruk & Pavliuk 2022). Concurrently, several Central and Eastern European states, which had only recently regained their independence following the disintegration of the USSR and the dissolution of the CIS, increasingly sought to become members of the North Atlantic Alliance. This development prompted a more critical stance from Moscow (Götz, Hamilton & Spohr 2019). In an attempt to temper this response, Polish President Lech Wałęsa succeeded in issuing a joint communiqué with Yeltsin during a meeting in Warsaw in August 1993, which asserted that Poland's NATO membership "is not contrary to the interest of any state, including Russia" (Sarotte 2025).

Declassified correspondence between Borys Yeltsin and Bill Clinton, made public in 2018, reveals that in 1993, the Russian president harbored reservations about NATO's expansion, yet did not fundamentally oppose it. Yeltsin acknowledged that the integration of Eastern European countries into the Alliance did not necessarily imply that such a move was directed against Russia. However, he emphasized the necessity of considering Russian public opinion and the prevailing sentiments within the Russian political elite. According to the National Security Archive (2018), the Russian leadership's opposition to NATO enlargement at the time can be understood more as an internal political maneuver, aimed at maintaining the support of a segment of Yeltsin's electorate that longed for the era of communism.

To alleviate tensions in relations with post-socialist countries, the Alliance initiated the Partnership for Peace (PfP) program in 1994, which was made available to all European nations, including those that had previously been members of the Warsaw Pact. The primary aim of this program was to enhance NATO's military cooperation with partner states and to promote stability within Europe. It offered tailored arrangements for each participant, allowing countries to define their priorities, pace, and scope of engagement with the Alliance. In the view of President Clinton, the PfP program represented a gradual path towards eventual NATO membership. Conversely, President Yeltsin perceived the initiative as a pragmatic compromise, whereby Eastern European countries would engage with NATO, but in a manner more palatable to the Russian Federation (Schuette 2023).

The course of regulating relations and fostering cooperation between Moscow and the Alliance progressed as intended. This continued collaboration culminated in the signing of the NATO-Russia Founding Act in 1997. Through this agreement, the parties – NATO and the Russian Federation – outlined a trajectory for the future development of their relations. They reaffirmed their commitment to the principles enshrined in the UN Charter and the Helsinki Act. Furthermore, the agreement explicitly asserted that "[NATO and Russia] ... will respect the sovereignty, independence and territorial integrity of all states and their inalienable right to choose the means of ensuring their security, the inviolability of borders, and the right of peoples to self-determination" (NATO 1997). Notably, while the treaty did not include any provisions regarding NATO's expansion, it did reference the inclusion of "new members" within the bloc.

At the NATO summit held a few weeks later, the Alliance formally extended membership invitations to three former members of the Warsaw Pact – Poland, Hungary, and the Czech Republic. Furthermore, on 9 July 1997, immediately following the Madrid NATO summit, the Charter on a Distinctive Partnership between Ukraine and the North Atlantic Treaty Organization was signed. By the Charter, the Ukraine-NATO Commission was established, tasked with ensuring the effective implementation of its provisions, conducting a comprehensive assessment of the development of relations between Ukraine and NATO, and planning future activities to enhance or further develop

cooperation between Ukraine and the Alliance (NATO 2023). This initiative served to mitigate the Russian Federation's cautious opposition to NATO's enlargement. The accession of the former Warsaw Pact states – namely Poland, the Czech Republic, and Hungary – to NATO in 1999 marked a significant shift in the European security architecture and paved the way for NATO's continued expansion eastwards. However, it is important to acknowledge that, for the Russian leadership, the “red line” has never been the former socialist countries, but rather the former Soviet republics, with the potential exception of the Baltic States.

NATO-Russia relations in the twenty-first century

At this particular historical juncture, the relationship between Moscow and the North Atlantic Alliance was predominantly influenced by the stance of the Russian leadership, with President Volodymyr Putin playing a central role. Over the subsequent two decades, the Kremlin's position on the Alliance, and specifically its expansion, experienced significant shifts, ranging from cautious cooperation to overt hostility. During his initial term, Putin did not vigorously oppose the accession of several former socialist states, including the post-Soviet nations of Lithuania, Latvia, and Estonia, considering that their inclusion in NATO would not present a direct threat to Russia. Furthermore, concerning Ukraine's potential membership in the Alliance, Putin did not categorically dismiss the possibility. He asserted that this matter should be determined by Ukraine and NATO as two sovereign partners and maintained that such a development would not adversely affect relations between Kyiv and Moscow (Bugayova, Stepanenko & Kagan 2023).

In 2002, during the summit of the North Atlantic Alliance in Rome, the President of the Russian Federation characterized the relationship between Russia and NATO as one transitioning from confrontation to cooperation. He affirmed Russia's commitment to international law and its agreements with NATO, referencing key documents such as the United Nations Charter, the Helsinki Final Act, and the Charter of the Organization for Security and Cooperation in Europe (Bugayova, Stepanenko & Kagan 2023). The summit culminated in the signing of the declaration “NATO-Russia Relations: A New Quality”, a pivotal document that enhanced both military and humanitarian collaboration between the Russian Federation and the Alliance, particularly in the domains of counter-terrorism, joint military exercises, and arms control (NATO 2002a). This declaration led to the establishment of the NATO-Russia Council, an advisory body through which the Russian Federation and NATO member states continued to advance cooperation on a broad spectrum of security concerns. The Council remained operational until the annexation of Crimea in 2014, after which cooperation between the Russian Federation and NATO was suspended (NATO 2002b).

Turning to the events of the 2000s, it is pertinent to observe that, following a promising outset to the decade, the rhetoric emanating from the Kremlin regarding NATO underwent a notable shift in subsequent years. Gradually, what had initially been official support for NATO, coupled with a stance of non-opposition to its expansion, transformed into increasing discontent. This dissatisfaction was articulated most prominently in the infamous speech delivered by President Volodymyr Putin at the Munich Security Conference in 2007.

In this address, the Russian leader explicitly argued that NATO's enlargement had little to do with the Alliance's modernization or the enhancement of regional security; rather, he contended, it represented a provocation directed against the Russian Federation. Moreover, he referred to the assurances allegedly made by the West following the dissolution of the Warsaw Pact (Prezident Rossii 2007). It is from this juncture that the myth of Western guarantees against NATO's eastern expansion began to take root, framed as a violation by Western states. In the years that followed, the Russian

government strategically incorporated this myth into the broader discourse of "de-NATOisation", positing that NATO's post-Cold War expansion not only posed a direct threat to Russia but also constituted a breach of Western promises not to pursue such a course of action.

In the subsequent 2008 year, at the Bucharest Summit, the Alliance extended an invitation for membership to both Ukraine and Georgia. This decision provoked an overt display of dissatisfaction from the Russian leadership, which expressed a strong disapproval of NATO's expansion. This stance was formally articulated in the 2008 Foreign Policy Concept of the Russian Federation, which explicitly stated: "Russia maintains a negative attitude towards NATO expansion, particularly about the plans for admitting Ukraine and Georgia as members of the alliance, as well as the general approach of NATO's military infrastructure towards Russian borders..." (Prezident Rossii 2008). Reflecting on these events, it is now evident that the developments of 2008 – specifically, the inclusion of Ukraine and Georgia's Euro-Atlantic prospects in the NATO Bucharest Summit declaration and the potential realization of this plan – represented a pivotal moment in the series of events that culminated in Russia's military aggression against Georgia in 2008, and subsequently against Ukraine in 2014 and 2022.

As President Putin's aspirations to position Russia as a dominant regional power intensified, Moscow's posture towards NATO became progressively more inflexible. The Russian authorities framed their military actions against Ukraine in 2014 as a necessary response to the perceived obligation to "protect the Russian-speaking population". Concurrently, animosity towards NATO and resistance to its expansion remained grounded in disinformation and myths, with the primary narrative being the alleged "betrayal" by NATO of its purported assurances against eastern expansion – assurances which, in fact, never existed. This narrative provided the Russian leadership with an additional pretext for its aggressive stance towards neighboring states.

Factors contributing to Russian opposition to NATO enlargement

The primary global objective of the Russian Federation, in broad terms, is to counter the West and replace the current liberal, legal international system with a "new world order", wherein the influence of the West will be substantially diminished. NATO, as the central institution underpinning the collective West, serves as the cornerstone of contemporary security arrangements. Consequently, NATO, as a pivotal element of the liberal international order, is expected to play a leading role in defending the existing global status quo against challenges posed by revisionist powers, such as the Kremlin. Indeed, as highlighted previously, Russia articulated its objectives and demands concerning NATO in the "Putin ultimatum" at the close of 2021 (MID RF 2021b). The document reveals that the Kremlin's opposition to NATO's expansion and continued presence in Central and Eastern Europe is not only deeply entrenched but also significantly influences various facets of the Russian Federation's domestic and foreign policy.

Moscow's justifications for the deNATOisation of Eastern Europe can be categorized into three main areas: security and stability, ideological considerations, and domestic political factors (Milano 1998). The security rationale, as articulated by Russian officials, concerns the perceived necessity of a buffer zone between the Russian Federation and the West, which would serve as an exclusive sphere of Moscow's interests. Since the 1990s, the Kremlin has regarded the territories of former Soviet republics and Soviet satellite states as its sphere of influence. This includes countries in Eastern and Central Europe, as well as Central Asia. In accordance with this rationale, by joining NATO or permitting the presence of Western military forces on their territories, states such as Ukraine, Georgia, Latvia, and Poland are believed to be contributing to the emergence of a direct military threat to Russia

(Milano 1998). Under the administration of President Putin, the Kremlin has openly rejected the current European security framework, which has been shaped over several decades by international agreements, including the Helsinki Final Act (1975). This foundational document enshrined the principle of state sovereignty and the right of nations to independently determine their security arrangements and military alliances. In the present context, Russia views NATO's expansion as a direct threat to its security, while invoking non-existent assurances regarding NATO's non-expansion eastward as part of its justification (Spohr 2022).

Volodymyr Putin's preoccupation with the notion that NATO's engagement with post-Soviet states extends beyond mere cooperation, and constitutes a direct threat to Russia by progressively moving its infrastructure closer to Russian borders, is evident. In his nearly hour-long address on the evening of 21 February 2022, the Russian President not only articulated a series of detailed historical grievances concerning Ukraine but also asserted that the United States and NATO "have commenced the shameless development of Ukrainian territory as a potential theatre for military operations". Furthermore, he reiterated the position that any further enlargement of NATO is deemed unacceptable by the Russian Federation (The Guardian 2022).

In reality, neither the United States nor NATO ever pursued a grand strategy aimed at detaching Ukraine from Russia's sphere of influence, incorporating it into the Alliance, and thereby posing a threat to Russia. On the contrary, a nuclear-free Ukraine was intentionally kept outside NATO, a status it continues to hold to this day. The Alliance's late declarations regarding Ukraine's eventual membership, notably articulated in the 2008 Bucharest Summit Declaration, were not part of a comprehensive strategic vision. Rather, they represented inadequate attempts to address Ukraine's increasing vulnerability in the face of escalating tensions with Russia.

The ideological factor is, in turn, constructed around post-Soviet Russian revanchist and imperialist ideologies. A profound sense of humiliation, stemming from the defeat in the Cold War, the erosion of former power, and the loss of its role in the international balance of power, remains a central determinant in shaping, and continuing to influence, the behavior of the Russian Federation in the global arena. The legacy of Soviet-era authority constitutes a fundamental element in shaping the current foreign policy ambitions of the Russian state. Additionally, the broad-based antagonism towards the North Atlantic Alliance can be traced to historical hostility dating back to the Cold War and an unwavering resistance to the loss of its great power status (Kuzio 1997). This ideological perspective is further reinforced by the fact that a significant majority of contemporary Russian officials have backgrounds rooted in various institutions of the former Soviet state, ranging from security agencies to the media. Given that many of these decision-makers were raised and launched their careers during the East-West confrontation, remnants of Cold War-era thinking remain deeply entrenched within the Russian foreign policy establishment (Götz, Hamilton & Spohr 2019).

Regarding domestic political factors, the range of reasons for opposing NATO expansion among the three groups of arguments has undergone the most significant changes. In the 1990s, when examining the reasons behind Russia's opposition to NATO's enlargement, researchers primarily focused on the attitudes of various political forces within the newly established Russian Federation. Liberal reformers contended that successful relations with the West were intrinsically linked to the process of domestic political and economic reforms. These reformers supported integration with Western institutions, such as NATO, the European Union, and the G7. For them, NATO expansion was perceived as a logical step towards European integration, which they believed Russia should eventually pursue. Conversely, anti-Western factions aimed to restore "Russian greatness" by rejecting the Western model of development. From their perspective, NATO's enlargement represented the actions

of anti-Russian forces in the West, which diminished Russia to the status of a second-rate state and insulted its national dignity. In contrast, moderate nationalists in Russia adopted a more pragmatic view of European political realities, acknowledging that NATO expansion would proceed regardless of Russia's approval. In their view, Russia's participation in the Partnership for Peace program and subsequent cooperation with NATO represented a strategic compromise, offering cooperation in return for agreements on other political and economic issues (Milano 1998).

In the 21st century, the relevance of such an analysis has diminished. Following Volodymyr Putin's rise to power in Russia, coupled with the gradual centralization and authoritarian consolidation of authority, the domestic political opposition to NATO expansion has assumed a new character. Putin's tenure is defined by the unequivocal dominance of anti-Western political forces. While the Russian Federation nominally hosts a contingent of "pro-Western" forces – referred to as systemic opposition – whose leaders regularly partake in the presidential and parliamentary elections, it must be acknowledged that this is merely a political spectacle aimed at external observers. In reality, both systemic and non-systemic opposition are virtually non-existent within the Russian Federation, with power having been fully concentrated in the hands of the current Kremlin leadership for the past 25 years. Consequently, the most significant domestic political threat to Moscow is the prospect of a genuine democratic opposition emerging. Such a development could be exemplified by the democratic processes and transformations observed in other post-Soviet and post-socialist nations, which, in turn, have opted for a pro-Western policy orientation and, consequently, membership in the Western security bloc – the North Atlantic Alliance (Person & McFaul 2022). Of particular importance, and potentially hazardous in this regard, is the example of Ukraine – a post-Soviet state that, historically, was a fundamental part of the Russian Empire and the USSR. Following the collapse of the socialist bloc, Ukraine faced considerable difficulties and obstacles but chose a Western-oriented developmental path. This direction is unacceptable within the framework of contemporary Russian political vision, as it contradicts long-standing propagandistic narratives regarding the inseparable relationship between Russia and Ukraine, as well as the purported "brotherhood" of their peoples (De Witte 2022).

It is not without significance that it was after the wave of "color revolutions" in Georgia (2003) and, more notably, Ukraine (2004), that President Putin increasingly became preoccupied with the preservation of the existing regime within the Russian Federation. In the aftermath of these events, he began to characterize NATO's expansion as a direct threat to Russia's national security. This assertion provided the Russian leader with a convenient rationale to counter the dissemination of Western values in neighboring states. Indeed, the developments observed in Ukraine over the past two decades presented a scenario that could potentially unfold within Russia itself, posing an existential challenge for Putin.

Moscow perceives Western-aligned governments in post-Soviet states as a potential threat to its strategic interests. In 2008, Russia launched an invasion of Georgia, ostensibly to support pro-Russian separatists in the regions of Abkhazia and South Ossetia. This military intervention, which took the West by surprise, served as a clear signal: Moscow would not tolerate the establishment of a pro-Western regime on its southern borders and was willing to deploy military force to prevent it. The invasion occurred shortly after the NATO summit in Bucharest in April 2008, during which Georgia and Ukraine were promised a potentially ambiguous path to membership in the Alliance.

When Russia initiated its invasion of Ukraine in 2014, the issue of Ukraine's potential NATO membership was not on the agenda. This was due to the enactment in 2010 of the Law of Ukraine on the Principles of Domestic and Foreign Policy, which enshrined the country's non-aligned status. At

that time, Ukraine was on the cusp of finalizing an Association Agreement with the European Union, the implementation of which would inevitably result in a gradual diminution of Russian influence within Ukraine. Consequently, it was not NATO that posed a threat to Russia, but rather the aspiration of the Ukrainian people for a vibrant democracy and closer integration with the European community. As Latvian Prime Minister Arturs Krišjanis Karinš aptly noted, “Moscow is not afraid of NATO forces, but of Ukrainian democracy” (Edelman & Kramer 2022). One of the primary motivations behind Russia’s aggression can be traced to the Kremlin’s perception that democracy – despite its imperfections, allowing the electorate to alter the president and the composition of the parliament through democratic elections – represents a profound existential threat to Putin’s authoritarian regime. The key to counteracting Moscow’s policy of DeNATOisation and restoring a solid basis of regional security in Europe is decisive concrete action in the direction of Ukraine’s future accession to NATO. Kyiv’s membership in the Alliance is the only long-term means of deterring future Russian attacks. As long as it is fighting, Ukraine will not join NATO – that is clear. But already now, to prevent Russia from constantly threatening Kyiv in the long term, the Alliance should seriously consider the scenario of how and when it will be able to accept Ukraine so that the issue of Ukrainian membership moves forward. If, as a result of the fighting, Russia retains control over part of the Ukrainian territory (an extremely undesirable outcome for Ukraine and the West, which they will try their best to prevent and will never recognize the captured regions as part of the Russian Federation), the territory under the control of the Ukrainian government must be protected from future threats through membership in to prevent Russia and further inflame instability in Europe. In the future, much will depend on the success of Ukrainian defense operations, the liberation of its territory, and further reforms of the defense sector. Ukraine already has the most capable, battle-hardened army in Europe, which will become an asset, not a liability, to the Alliance (Sydoruk, Pavliuk & Avhustiuk 2023).

Conclusion

DeNATOisation represents one of the principal objectives of the Russian Federation in its conflict with Ukraine, as well as in its broader confrontation with the West. The Kremlin justifies this aim by asserting that NATO’s expansion after the Cold War posed a threat to Russian security and allegedly violated assurances previously given by Western powers not to enlarge the Alliance. This narrative of historical grievance is strategically utilized by the Kremlin to legitimize its efforts to subjugate Ukraine and to prevent further NATO expansion into the post-Soviet space. However, in reality, Moscow has no legitimate grounds for such claims, as it failed to secure a formal agreement on NATO’s non-expansion during the negotiations surrounding German reunification. Moreover, even if such a verbal assurance had been made, it would not implicate either the United States or Ukraine in Russia’s decision to initiate a full-scale invasion on 24 February 2022. This rationale also fails to provide any moral or legal justification for the targeting of Ukrainian civilian infrastructure, including maternity hospitals and children’s playgrounds.

For informed decision-making in the future, particularly during peace negotiations, it is essential to accurately interpret historical facts and dispel myths that could, in effect, exonerate Moscow from some of its responsibilities. Putin continues to argue that any peace agreement in Ukraine must address the “root causes” of the conflict – NATO expansion. To acquiesce to such a viewpoint would involve conceding to Moscow’s demands and endorsing a peace settlement that lacks safeguards against the resurgence of Russian aggression, thereby diminishing NATO’s ability to defend its European members. Given the high stakes involved, it is crucial to prevent the deNATOisation of both Ukraine and Europe. These facts clearly demonstrate that the war chosen by the Kremlin in

Ukraine is not a defensive operation in response to Western interference, as has long been claimed by some neorealists and Russian ideologues. Rather, it constitutes the opening salvo of a conflict aimed not only at subjugating Ukraine but also at reshaping the European and global order.

The Ukrainians are sure to have the right to decide independently on acceptable conditions for ending the war and the future geopolitical orientation of the state. However, any decision on Europe's security architecture and changes in the balance of power on the continent cannot be approved without the participation of the United States and its European allies. Therefore, they may have to decide whether to leave NATO open for Ukraine and other former Soviet republics seeking accession. If Ukraine declares a nonaligned or neutral status or NATO refuses to expand further, an agreement will need to be found that a nonaligned or militarily neutral Ukraine can be confident of its security by maintaining close ties with the collective West. Only the settlement that preserves an independent Ukraine with reliable means to ensure its security (the best option is its accession to NATO) can be considered a success. However, if Ukraine gets stuck in no man's land on the outskirts of Russia and without NATO protection (this certainly applies to Georgia and Moldova as well), it will have dangerous consequences in the future.

References

- Bugayova, N., Stepanenko K. & F. Kagan. (2023). *Weakness is Lethal: Why Putin Invaded Ukraine and How the War Must End*. Institute for the Study of War.
<https://understandingwar.org/backgrounder/weakness-lethal-why-putin-invaded-ukraine-and-how-war-must-end>.
- Ciuriak, D. (2023). *NATO's Enlargement and Russia's Interests: Existential Threat or Invaluable External Discipline?* <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4202776>.
- Charap, S. (2022). How to Break the Cycle of Conflict With Russia. Seeking Consensus Isn't Appeasement – It's Pragmatism. *Foreign Affairs*.
<https://www.foreignaffairs.com/articles/russia-fsu/2022-02-07/how-break-cycle-conflict-russia>.
- De Witte, M. (2022). Putin sees Ukrainian democracy as a threat, undermines his sense of the Russian mission. *Stanford Report*. <https://news.stanford.edu/stories/2022/03/putin-sees-ukrainian-democracy-threat-undermines-russias-mission>.
- Deutschland.de. (2017). *Two plus Four Treaty*.
<https://www.deutschland.de/en/topic/politics/development-dialogue/25th-anniversary-of-the-two-plus-four-treaty>.
- Edelman, E. & D. Kramer. (2022). Keep NATO's Door Open to Ukraine. Washington Shouldn't Grant Putin the Sphere of Influence He Wants. *Foreign Affairs*.
<https://www.foreignaffairs.com/articles/ukraine/2022-01-31/keep-natos-door-open-ukraine>.
- Foreign Affairs. (2022). *Was NATO Enlargement a Mistake? Foreign Affairs Asks the Experts*.
<https://www.foreignaffairs.com/ask-the-experts/2022-04-19/was-nato-enlargement-mistake>.
- Götz, E., Hamilton, D. & K. Spohr. (2019). *Open door: NATO and Euro-Atlantic security after the Cold War*. <https://transatlanticrelations.org/publications/open-door-nato-and-euro-atlantic-security-after-the-cold-war/>.

- Haslam, J. (2024). *Hubris: The Origins of Russia's War Against Ukraine*. Bloomsbury.
- Kimmage, M. (2022). Time for NATO to Close Its Door. The Alliance Is Too Big – and Too Provocative – for Its Own Good. *Foreign Affairs*. <https://www.foreignaffairs.com/articles/russia-fsu/2022-01-17/time-nato-close-its-door>.
- Kuzio, T. (1997). NATO enlargement: The view from the East. *European Security*, 6(1): 48-62. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09662839708407298>.
- Lanoszka, A. (2021). How NATO should greet Russia's 'draft treaty'. *Britain's World*. <https://www.geostrategy.org.uk/britains-world/how-nato-should-greet-russias-draft-treaty/>.
- Maitra, S. (2021). NATO Enlargement, Russia, and Balance of Threat. *Canadian Military Journal*, 21(3): 35-46.
- McFaul, M. (2022). How to Make a Deal With Putin. Only a Comprehensive Pact Can Avoid War. *Foreign Affairs*. <https://www.foreignaffairs.com/articles/europe/2022-02-11/how-make-deal-putin>.
- Mearsheimer, J. J. (2014). Why the Ukraine Crisis Is the West's Fault. The Liberal Delusions That Provoked Putin. *Foreign Affairs*. <https://www.foreignaffairs.com/articles/russia-fsu/2014-08-18/why-ukraine-crisis-west-s-fault>.
- MID RF. (2021a). Dogovor mezhdru Rossiyskoy Federatsiyey i Soedinennymi Shtatami Ameriki o garantiyah bezopasnosti. https://mid.ru/ru/foreign_policy/rso/nato/1790818/.
- MID RF. (2021b). Soglashenie o merah obespecheniya bezopasnosti Rossiyskoy Federatsii i gosudarstv-chlenov Organizatsii Severoatlanticheskogo dogovora. https://mid.ru/ru/foreign_policy/rso/nato/1790803/.
- Milano, J. (1998). *NATO Enlargement from the Russian Perspective*. <https://www.hsdl.org/c/view?docid=453037>.
- National Security Archive. (2018). *NATO Expansion: What Yeltsin Heard*. https://nsarchive.gwu.edu/briefing-book/russia-programs/2018-03-16/nato-expansion-what-yeltsin-heard#_ednref12.
- NATO. (1997). Founding Act on Mutual Relations, Cooperation and Security between NATO and the Russian Federation. https://www.nato.int/cps/su/natohq/official_texts_25468.htm.
- NATO. (2002a). NATO-Russia Relations: A New Quality. https://www.nato.int/cps/en/natohq/official_texts_19572.htm?selectedLocale=en.
- NATO. (2002b). NATO-Russia Council. https://www.nato.int/cps/uk/natohq/topics_50091.htm?selectedLocale=en.
- NATO. (2023). NATO-Ukraine Commission (1997-2023). https://www.nato.int/cps/en/natohq/topics_50319.htm.
- OBSE. (2024). Vystuplenie rukovoditelya Delegatsii Rossiyskoy Federatsii na peregovorah v Vene po voprosam voennoy bezopasnosti i kontrolya nad vooruzheniyami K. Yu. Gavrilova na 1074-m plenarnom zasedanii Foruma OBSE po sotrudnichestvu v oblasti bezopasnosti (17 aprelya 2024 goda). <https://www.osce.org/files/f/documents/6/b/567707.pdf>.
- Ohryzko, V. Sohn, R. & A. Gic. (2024). The West Must Stop Protecting Russia from the Consequences of its Actions. Royal United Services Institute. <https://www.rusi.org/explore-our-research/publications/commentary/west-must-stop-protecting-russia-consequences-its-actions>.

- Person, R. & M. McFaul. (2022). What Putin Fears Most. *Journal of Democracy*, 33(2): 18-27. <https://www.journalofdemocracy.org/articles/what-putin-fears-most/>.
- Pifer, S. (2014). Did NATO Promise Not to Enlarge? Gorbachev Says "No". Brookings. <https://www.brookings.edu/articles/did-nato-promise-not-to-enlarge-gorbachev-says-no/>.
- Pifer, S. (2021). Russia's draft agreements with NATO and the United States: Intended for rejection? Brookings. <https://www.brookings.edu/articles/russias-draft-agreements-with-nato-and-the-united-states-intended-for-rejection/>.
- Prezident Rossii. (2007). Vystuplenie i diskussiya na Myunhenskoy konferentsii po voprosam politiki bezopasnosti. <http://kremlin.ru/events/president/transcripts/24034>.
- Prezident Rossii. (2008). Kontseptsiya vneshney politiki Rossiyskoy Federatsii. <http://static.kremlin.ru/media/events/files/41d447a0ce9f5a96bdc3>.
- Sarotte, M. E. (2025). Why They Fight. What's at Stake in the Blame Game Over Ukraine. *Foreign Affairs*. <https://www.foreignaffairs.com/reviews/why-they-fight>.
- Schuette, C. (2023). Russian Disinformation on NATO Expansion and the War in Ukraine. *Journal of Strategic Security*, 16(4): 34-56. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/48751614>.
- Spohr, K. (2022). Exposing the myth of Western betrayal of Russia over NATO's eastern enlargement. *LSE British Politics and Policy*. <https://blogs.lse.ac.uk/politicsandpolicy/exposing-the-myth-of-western-betrayal-of-russia/>.
- Sydoruk, T. & V. Pavliuk. (2022). NATO Enlargement as a false excuse for Russia's War against Ukraine. *Strategic Panorama*. 35-44. <https://doi.org/10.53679/2616-9460.specialissue.2022.04>.
- Sydoruk, T., Pavliuk, V. & M. Avhustiuk. (2023) The Impact of the Russian-Ukrainian War on European Security. *Romanian Journal of Political Science*. 23(2): 43-55.
- Sydoruk, T., Pavliuk, V. & A. Shuliak (2023). Russia's war against Ukraine and the transformation of the Euro-Atlantic Security Architecture. *Politics in Central Europe*. 19(2): 305-323.
- The Guardian. (2022). Putin orders troops into eastern Ukraine on 'peacekeeping'. www.theguardian.com/world/2022/feb/21/ukraine-putin-decide-recognition-breakaway-states-today.
- Thom, F. (2021). What Does the Russian Ultimatum to the West Mean? *Desk Russie*. <https://desk-russie.info/2021/12/30/what-does-the-russian-ultimatum-to-the-west-mean.html>.